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Scientific Research Institute of Medical Prophylaxis named after V. Akhundov,
Senior laboratory assistant***Abstract**

The aim of the study was to study indicators of cellular and humoral immunity in patients with toxoplasmosis at different stages of the disease. 77 patients with clinical manifestations of exacerbation of chronic toxoplasmosis were examined. Labrinks flow cytometry CD3, CD4, CD8, IRI, CD4/CD8 ratio and concentration of serum immunoglobulins on Stat fax 4700 analyzer (IgA, IgM, IgG immunoglobulins) were determined. Group 1 included 58 patients with a transition to the latent phase of the disease (cyclic course of the manifest form of chronic toxoplasmosis), group 2 - 19 patients with re-exacerbation of chronic toxoplasmosis within a year after treatment (chronic form of toxoplasmosis). In accordance with the goals and objectives of this work, patients were examined in the dynamics of the disease: during the exacerbation period and immediately after immunomodulation. All patients received anti-inflammatory, antioxidant treatment, as well as immunomodulators. The control group consisted of 20 clinically healthy individuals.

As a result of research, it was found that during the period of exacerbation (reactivation) with a cyclical course, a statistically significant increase in the number of CD8+, as well as a decrease in the level of IgA, is observed. CD8

CD4/CD8 ratio due to increased lymphocytes, CD4+ and CD8+ decreased in all patients after immunomodulation. However, if CD4+ decreased by 5% and CD8+ decreased by 11% during the cyclic course of the disease, the opposite trend was recorded in the recurrent course: CD4+ decreased by 25% and CD8+ decreased by 10% in patients with a repeated course of chronic toxoplasmosis with uniform normalization of IgA. CD4+ increased significantly in CD8+ (30%) is accompanied by an increase. The results of the examination of patients with chronic toxoplasmosis 6 months after the course of treatment show that a course of therapy during the cyclic course of the disease leads to the transition of the disease to a chronic latent form.

Studies have shown that immune processes leading to clinical manifestations of reactivation of chronic toxoplasmosis are characterized by certain differences in patients with a persistent positive effect of immunocorrection and in patients with a repeated course of this clinical form of the disease.

Keywords: chronic toxoplasmosis, cellular and humoral immunity.

The relevance of the study of toxoplasmosis is dictated, first of all, by the fact that this pathology is associated with immunodeficiency conditions (especially with HIV infection) [1]. The long-term persistence of the pathogen is accompanied by a "floating" concentration of specific antibodies produced by a clone of antigen-specific memory B-lymphocytes. This stage of the disease is called chronic toxoplasmosis (XT) and is a natural consequence of the acute process [2, 3, 4]. A sufficient number of T- and B-memory cells determines the absence of clinical manifestations of the disease (the latent course of CT). However, in some cases (1-

5% of infected people), the latent infection is reactivated. This category includes "immunocompromised" individuals, including those with secondary immunodeficiency (HIV infection, as well as iatrogenic, uncontrolled antibacterial, cytostatic, and glucocorticoid therapy) [5.6.7

The aim of the study was to study indicators of cellular and humoral immunity in patients with toxoplasmosis at different stages of the disease.

Materials and methods. 77 patients with clinical manifestations of exacerbation of HT (reactivation of the latent form of HT) were examined. The diagnosis

was detected on the basis of clinical and laboratory data (presence of toxoplasma-specific Ig G, enzyme immunoassay ELISA, Vector-Best test system) and confirmed by the polymerase chain reaction method (PCR in blood serum)., includes determining the ratio of CD8CD4/CD8 and determination of IgA, IgM, IgG concentration of serum immunoglobulins in the blood. During the statistical processing of the obtained data, parametric statistical methods (Student's criterion), frequency analysis, and the method of calculating diagnostic value coefficients were used. All patients were divided into groups according to the effectiveness of therapy. Group 1 - 58 patients with the transition of the disease to the latent phase (cyclic course of clarity). forms of chronic toxoplasmosis), group 2 - 19 patients with re-exacerbation of HT during the next year after treatment (recurrent course of the manifest form of chronic toxoplasmosis). In accordance with the goals and objectives of this work, patients were examined in

the dynamics of the disease: during the exacerbation period and immediately after immunomodulation. All patients received anti-inflammatory, antioxidant treatment, as well as immunomodulators. Control group - 20 clinically healthy individuals.

Results. It was determined that significant changes in the studied immunological parameters occur during the exacerbation period (table 1) in patients with CT. Thus, despite the absence of significant statistical differences in patients with a cyclic course of the disease, CD8 was significantly higher in the former compared to those with relapse. Compared to indicators of the immune status in the latent form of XT, the period of exacerbation (reactivation) in the cyclic course is characterized by a statistically significant increase in the number of CD8+, as well as a decrease in the level of IgA. and a decrease in the CD4/CD8 ratio due to an increase in CD8 lymphocytes.

Table 1

Indicators of immune status during disease exacerbation in patients with chronic toxoplasmosis (X ± m)

Indicators	Xmin- Xmax	Groups					
		Control		Cyclic flow		Recurrent course	
		X	± m	X	± m	X	± m
CD3+, cells/μl	688-1955	1321	50	1290	40	1307	35
CD4+, cells/μl	355-1213	784	30	907	20	814	25
CD8+, cells/μl	145-800	472	50	870*	50	893**	30
CD4/CD8	0.83-6.1	3.46	1.5	1.45*	1.5	1.37**	0.5
IgA g/l	1.5-2.2	1.85	0.5	0.77*	0.5	0.73**	0.5
IgM g/l	0.8-1.1	0.95	0.3	1.0	0.3	1.1	0.3
IgG g/l	4.5-8.5	6.5	1.7	7.5	0.3	8.3	0.3
IgG to T. gondii, ME/ml	0-30	15	5	17	5	19	0.5

* - p<0.05, (comparison with control group)

** - p<0.01 (comparison between groups with cyclic and repeated XT).

The analysis of the conducted studies (tables 2-3) shows that, in addition to the changes in the immune system common to both groups of HT patients, there were significant differences in the dynamics of the studied parameters that increased over time. Thus, CD4+ and CD8+ reduction was observed in all patients immediately after immunomodulation. However, if CD4+ decreased by 5% and CD8+ decreased by 11% during the cyclic course of the disease, repeated the opposite trend was recorded: CD4+ decreased by 25%, and CD8+ decreased by 10%. (Table 2).

During the month, different results were obtained in the dynamics of the parameters of the immune status of the studied patients (Table 3). The number of CD4+

increased to values greater than the period of exacerbation, a further decrease in the number of CD8+ was observed, and an increase in the concentration of IgA was noted. Unidirectional dynamics of IgG concentration was noted in both groups of patients (a decrease in the number of IgG-producing lymphocytes and the concentration of specific immunoglobulins). The results of a comprehensive (clinical and immunological) examination of patients 3-6 months after treatment deserve special attention.

The results of examination of patients with manifest forms of HT 6 months after the course of treatment show that a course of therapy during the cyclic course of the disease leads to the transition of the disease to a chronic latent form.

Table 2

Indicators of immune status after treatment in patients with chronic toxoplasmosis

Indicators	Xmin- Xmax	Groups					
		Control		Cyclic flow		Recurrent course	
		X	± m	X	± m	X	± m
CD3+, cells/μl	688-1955	1319	50	1275	40	1329	35
CD4+, cells/μl	355-1213	780	30	917	20	824	25
CD8+, cells/μl	145-800	472	50	630*	50	993**	30
CD4/CD8	0.83-6.1	3.37	1.5	2.45*	1.5	2.27**	0.5
IgA g/l	1.5-2.2	1.80	0.5	0.87*	0.5	0.92**	0.5
IgM g/l	0.8-1.1	0.90	0.3	1.0	0.3	1.14	0.3
IgG g/l	4.5-8.5	5.5	1.7	7.5	0.3	8.7	0.3
IgG to T. gondii, ME/ml	0-30	13	5	17	5	21	5

*- p<0.05 (comparison with control group),

** - p<0.05 (comparison between groups with cyclic and repeated XT)

Table 3

Indicators of immune status in patients with chronic toxoplasmosis 1 month after treatment

Indicators	Xmin- Xmax	Groups					
		Control		Cyclic flow		Recurrent course	
		X	± m	X	± m	X	± m
CD-3+, cells/μl	688-1955	1641	50	1798	40	1576	35
CD-4+, cells/μl	355-1213	780	30	1010	20	978	25
CD8+, cells/μl	145-800	472	50	749	50	790	30
CD4/CD8	0.83-6.1	4.38	1.5	5.7	1.5	5.1	0.5
IgA g/l	1.5-2.2	1.77	0.5	1.7	0.5	1.95	0.5
IgM g/l	0.8-1.1	0.90	0.3	1.0	0.3	1.18	0.3
IgG g/l	4.5-8.5	6.5	1.7	8.1	0.3	8.3	0.3
IgG to T. gondii, ME/ml	0-30	15	5	17	5	26	5

Almost complete clinical remission is noted - complaints, symptoms of intoxication, manifestations of damage to the hepato-lienal system disappear, the size of peripheral lymph nodes decreases, and social adaptation of patients is restored. An increase in the concentration of Ig G tissue is detected, and the increase in CD4-lymphocytes corresponds to a proportional increase in the number of CD8-lymphocytes. Most of the investigated immunological parameters do not differ from those of latent form of XT. The long-term persistence of the pathogen is accompanied by a "floating" concentration of specific antibodies produced by a clone of antigen-specific memory B-lymphocytes. This stage of the disease is called chronic toxoplasmosis and is a natural consequence of the acute process. A sufficient number of T- and B-memory cells determines the absence of clinical manifestations of the disease (hidden course of HT). However, in some cases (1-5% of infected people), the latent infection is reactivated. This category includes "immunocompromised" individuals, including those with secondary immunodeficiency.

Results. Conducted studies show that the immune processes causing the clinical manifestations of XT reactivity are characterized by certain differences in patients with a stable positive effect of immunocorrection and in patients with a repeated course of this clinical form of the disease. Together with the currently available literature data, the results of our own research allow

us to speculate on some of the manifestations of chronic toxoplasmosis. During the recurrence of toxoplasma infection, signs of cellular immunity deficiency have been determined. The changes present, including the hyperproduction of IgM, are consistent with the presence of virus-induced immunosuppression caused by the prolonged stay of the virus in an active state. It can be assumed that in this case, the main target cells of the immunotropic effect of toxoplasma infection will be the general population of T-lymphocytes, which reflect humoral and T-cell immunity. These data indicate a violation of the antiviral defense of the body when the virus is in an active state.

Thus, the conducted studies showed the existence and nature of the relationship between the main direction and severity of immune disorders in patients and the characteristics of the clinical course of toxoplasma.

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